

Why should we try to think like scientists? Scientific reasoning and susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases

Vladimíra Čavojová^a, Jakub Šrol^a & Marek Jurkovič^a

^aInstitute of Experimental Psychology, Centre of Social and Psychological Sciences,
Slovak Academy of Sciences

Corresponding author:

Vladimíra Čavojová

Institute of Experimental Psychology, Centre of Social and Psychological Sciences,
Slovak Academy of Sciences

Dúbravská cesta 9, 841 04 Bratislava, Slovakia

Phone: + 421 - 2 - 5477 5625

Email: vladimira.cavojova@savba.sk

This is author accepted version of manuscript:

Čavojová, V., Šrol, J., & Jurkovič, M. (2020). Why should we try to think like scientists? Scientific reasoning and susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 34(1), 85-95.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.3595>

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This study was supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency by Grant Scheme No. APVV-16-0153: Cognitive failures— individual predictors and intervention possibilities.

ABSTRACT

This paper examines whether scientific-reasoning skills predict people's susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases. We used the recently developed Scientific-Reasoning Scale (SRS; Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017) because it measures the ability to read and evaluate scientific evidence. Alongside the SRS, 317 participants aged 18–30 years completed measures of thinking dispositions and cognitive ability to ascertain whether the SRS contributes specifically to susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases. Scientific reasoning correlated positively with dispositions towards analytic thinking and cognitive ability and negatively with dogmatism, epistemically suspect beliefs, and susceptibility to cognitive biases. Most importantly, it emerged as a significant predictor, contributing to both susceptibility to cognitive biases and to epistemically suspect beliefs over and above the other cognitive predictors. These results provide the first empirical evidence that scientific-reasoning ability is an important factor in protecting against epistemically suspect beliefs, and in aiding better decision-making among the non-scientific population.

Keywords: scientific reasoning; epistemically suspect beliefs; cognitive biases; intelligence

Introduction

While scientific-reasoning skills are the daily bread and butter for most people who will read this paper, lay people may find them rather obscure, outside their realm and capabilities, and, crucially, to have no direct relevance to their everyday lives. Yet, in the increasingly complex modern world, people regularly process information and face choices that require at least some basic level of scientific thinking. Consider the example of the many websites promoting healthy lifestyles that refer to the ‘latest scientific findings’ or a ‘return to natural remedies’. How do we know this advice or these products will actually help, and not do more harm? On one website, Goop.com, products advertised for sale include Propolis spray and Organic Citrus Digestive Bitters, but also Psychic Vampire Repellent (‘Spray around the aura to protect from psychic attack and emotional harm.’), Chill Child-Kid Calming Mist (‘Crystal and spiritual healer Zoe Taylor-Crane distils the mood-lifting, therapeutic powers of gemstones into gorgeous elixirs and mists meant to clear toxic energy, promote calm and creativity.’) and Everlasting Love (sold out). Believing in psychic vampires, ghosts, or witches is just one example of a belief that is unfounded in evidence. Scientific reasoning could help prospective customers weigh up the information on whether these ghastly creatures exist and save the money they spend on ineffective elixirs, talismans, or antidotes. These are just a couple of examples where scientific-reasoning skills could potentially prevent people from holding unfounded beliefs and making irrational decisions and invalid inferences.

For these reasons, researchers have, for some time now, been arguing about the need for civic scientific literacy (Miller, 1998, 2004), understood to mean having a sufficient level of understanding of scientific terms and constructs so as to be able to read a daily newspaper or magazine and understand the essence of the competing arguments on a

given dispute or controversy. Traditionally, scientific reasoning was viewed as thinking done by scientists (Dunbar & Klahr, 2012). Scientific reasoning has been seen as the mental processes we use when reasoning about the content of science and when engaged in typical scientific activities. It also refers to the specific types of reasoning frequently used in science (Dunbar & Fugelsang, 2005). Scientific reasoning is related to the broader concept of scientific literacy, which has at least three related dimensions: (1) knowledge of relevant scientific vocabulary and constructs; (2) understanding of the process of scientific inquiry; and (3) understanding of the impact of science on everyday life (Miller, 1998, 2004).

In past research, scientific literacy was mainly measured by having participants agree with items on which there is scientific consensus (Lobato & Zimmerman, 2018), related to a particular field of study or depending on number of years of science education (Díaz-Vilela & Alvarez, 2004; Grimmer & White, 1992; Johnson & Pigliucci, 2004), or through the use of knowledge-based tests (Johnson & Pigliucci, 2004; Kahan, 2017; McCloskey, 1983; Miller, 1983, 1998; Shtulman & Valcarcel, 2012). This type of test check people's understanding of basic scientific concepts, such as what an atom or DNA is, how long it takes the Earth to go around the Sun, or whether antibiotics help to kill viruses. The problem with measuring scientific literacy in this way is that knowledge of scientific concepts does not necessarily reflect a person's understanding of them (Johnson & Pigliucci, 2004), and that agreeing or disagreeing with politically controversial topics may often reflect people's concern for their cultural identity rather than their understanding of the actual science (Kahan, 2017; Kahan et al., 2012). Recently, however, this shortcoming has been addressed in the work of Drummond and Fischhoff (2017), in which they developed an individual-difference measure of scientific reasoning skills, which they defined as the 'skills needed to evaluate scientific

findings in terms of the factors that determine their quality' (p.1). This measure of scientific reasoning reflects a more applied understanding of the process of scientific inquiry (the second dimension of civic scientific literacy) rather than simply measuring scientific knowledge. Moreover, defined thus, scientific reasoning refers to the set of skills that people regularly need to evaluate evidence and adopt valid beliefs, or to make rational inferences and decisions.

Focusing on scientific reasoning as the ability to evaluate the quality of evidence, in our study we decided to examine the role scientific reasoning may play in two related domains of biased thinking: epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases.

The first research domain we drew upon, which concerns a type of everyday cognitive failure, is the study of epistemically suspect beliefs; that is, beliefs in the paranormal, conspiracy theories, and pseudoscience (Čavojová, Secarã, Jurkovič, & Šrol, 2018; E. Lobato, Mendoza, Sims, & Chin, 2014; Pennycook, Fugelsang, & Koehler, 2015). Research on epistemically suspect beliefs has so far uncovered several cognitive predictors in this domain. Perhaps the most studied are general tendency towards either intuitive, experiential, and automatic thinking, or analytic, reflective, and logical thinking. Several studies have shown that these intuitive and analytic thinking dispositions correlate with various epistemically suspect beliefs (Ballová Mikušková, 2018; Čavojová & Jurkovič, 2017; Lindeman & Aarnio, 2006; Pennycook, Cheyne, Barr, Koehler, & Fugelsang, 2015; Swami, Voracek, Stieger, Tran, & Furnham, 2014). Cognitive ability has also been associated with a weaker belief in epistemically suspect beliefs in a range of studies (Hergovich & Arendasy, 2005; Ståhl & van Prooijen, 2018; Stanovich, West, & Toplak, 2016), but only to a moderate extent. Importantly, while some of the previous research has shown that scientific literacy may play a role in protecting against various unsubstantiated beliefs, such as paranormal and

pseudoscientific claims (Aarnio & Lindeman, 2005; Bensley, Lilienfeld, & Powell, 2014; Fasce & Picó, 2019; Grimmer & White, 1992), other studies have not found a relationship among these variables (Goode, 2002; Johnson & Pigliucci, 2004; Lundström & Jakobsson, 2009; Majima, 2015; Walker, Hoekstra, & Vogl, 2002). These inconsistencies can at least partially be attributed to the aforementioned limitations in the measurement of scientific literacy. Nonetheless, we are not aware of any research so far focusing specifically on whether scientific reasoning abilities, as opposed to other aspects of broader scientific literacy, may play an important role in susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs. This we set out to examine in this study.

We argue that scientific reasoning ability may be important to whether a person adopts and holds different suspect beliefs, and for several reasons. First, many of the claims upon which some epistemically suspect beliefs are built have been directly disproven by science (Hines, 2002). Secondly, one factor which makes ‘alternative explanations’ such as conspiracy theories or pseudoscientific beliefs so widespread is that these claims do not need meet the strict criteria on consistency, coherency, and falsifiability applicable to scientific theories (e.g., Lewandowsky, Gignac, & Oberauer, 2013). Therefore, there is greater potential for conspiracy theories and pseudoscientific claims to spread among the general population and they have a higher explanatory power (they can explain many things at once). Lastly, the proponents of various epistemically suspect beliefs often adopt arguments that resemble scientific arguments (Harambam & Aupers, 2015) and/or base their claims on theories or methods that seem scientific but lack empirical evidence collected by scientific method (e.g., Tsai et al., 2012). This suggests that people who possess the rudimentary scientific reasoning skills and can use them to evaluate arguments, evidence, and theories, should be more able to recognise the shortcomings of the ‘alternative explanations’ that form the basis of epistemically

suspect beliefs and therefore should be less susceptible to adopting and holding those beliefs. The findings of Drummond and Fischhoff (2015) also show that people with better scientific reasoning are more likely to have beliefs consistent with the scientific consensus, above and beyond education, political and religious beliefs, and scores on two widely used measures of scientific literacy.

The second research paradigm we build upon in this paper is the study of heuristics and biases (H&B), begun by Tversky and Kahneman (1974). Research in this area shows that people are prone to systematic errors (i.e., biases) in judgment and decision-making because they rely on intuitive processing strategies (i.e., heuristics) even in situations where these strategies divert them from the logical considerations of the problem (Stanovich et al., 2016; Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). While there are known to be substantial individual differences in susceptibility to cognitive biases (Stanovich et al., 2016), to this day only a few factors – such as cognitive ability, thinking dispositions, cognitive reflection, and/or numeracy – have been empirically shown to independently drive these differences (Klaczynski, 2014; Šrol & Neys, n.d.; Toplak, West, & Stanovich, 2011). And even those identified factors do not drive susceptibility to all cognitive biases. For example, Stanovich and West (2008b) demonstrated that cognitive ability is related to performance in some, H&B tasks, such as outcome bias, ratio bias, belief bias, four-card section task, or overconfidence effect, but not in others, such as conjunction fallacy, myside bias, framing effect, sunk cost effect or anchoring effect. They also elaborate an explanation for these mixed findings: even though more intelligent people are more likely to possess the relevant knowledge (mindware) necessary to solve these tasks and to recognize the necessity to apply the knowledge, this is useful only for problems of intermediate difficulty (Kahneman & Frederick, 2002). Stanovich and West (2008b) call these two conditions error of comprehension

and mindware gap¹ and they build on Kahneman's and Frederick's explanation by adding the third condition – necessity for sustained cognitive decoupling, which is cognitively demanding and major source of the variability between cognitive ability and susceptibility to various H&B tasks.

As we have seen, these researchers (Stanovich, 2018; Stanovich & West, 2008b) argued that one of the components necessary for sound reasoning and decision-making is mindware, which is knowledge of the logical principles necessary for solving reasoning and decision-making tasks which are used to measure susceptibility to cognitive biases. Mindware instantiation (i.e., the level to which the available mindware is automatized) is theoretically recognised as being key to susceptibility to cognitive biases; yet, it has been largely neglected in empirical studies in the heuristics and biases paradigm (Šrol & Neys, n.d.; Stanovich, 2018). Nonetheless, it has been argued that scientific reasoning is part of the mindware required to do well on heuristics and biases tasks (Stanovich, 2018). This is because these problems require the ability to test hypotheses and evaluate evidence and draw conclusions, alongside probabilistic reasoning and, more generally, the propensity not to affirm the first conclusion that comes to mind but to think more deeply about the problem, look for counterevidence, and subsequently rethink answers (e.g., Stanovich et al., 2016). All these capabilities can be seen as important components of scientific reasoning ability, which is why we believe it is important to empirically examine whether scientific reasoning is part of crucial mindware for solving relevant heuristics and biases tasks.

¹ Similarly, De Neys and Bonnefon (2013) say that the current research of why people tend to cognitively fail can be divided into three main reasons: storage failure, monitoring failure, and inhibition failure.

While the research on epistemically suspect beliefs and on cognitive biases may appear quite distinct at first glance – the first focuses more on the various types of unfounded beliefs people have, and the second concentrates on the processes of reasoning and decision-making – there is growing evidence that the two domains are mutually interconnected. Empirical research conducted in the past couple of years shows that susceptibility to cognitive biases and susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs tend to correlate (Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015; Stanovich et al., 2016), and it has been suggested that some epistemically suspect beliefs may develop as a consequence of specific biases in probabilistic reasoning (Brotherton & French, 2014; Brugger & Graves, 1997; Rogers, Davis, & Fisk, 2009). The two also share some key common cognitive predictors, such as cognitive ability (Ståhl & van Prooijen, 2018) and the tendency towards intuitive/analytical thinking (e.g., Pennycook, Fugelsang, & Koehler, 2015). Several thinking dispositions implicated in susceptibility to both cognitive biases and to epistemically suspect beliefs (e.g., the need for cognition, faith in intuition, open-minded thinking) reflect, at least in part, the propensity to look for contradictory evidence and to consider opposing points of view instead of quickly making up one's mind on the basis of the first piece of information. This propensity is integral to scientific thinking and is essential for evaluating evidence. Therefore, we believe that scientific-reasoning skills may well represent another cognitive predictor which plays an essential role in protecting against both epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases during reasoning and decision-making.

To sum up, in this study we set out to examine whether scientific-reasoning skills predict people's susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases. While there are many tools for studying scientific reasoning, we decided to use the recently developed Scientific-Reasoning Scale (Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017). We

thought this tool particularly suitable because it was designed to measure the ability to read and evaluate scientific evidence. This is a substantial improvement over previously employed measures which relied primarily on people's knowledge of scientific concepts and/or specific scientific facts. We also used measures of thinking dispositions and cognitive ability as these two are among the best established cognitive predictors of cognitive biases (Klaczynski, 2014; Šrol & Neys, n.d.; Stanovich et al., 2016; Toplak et al., 2011) and epistemically suspect beliefs (Pennycook, Fugelsang, et al., 2015; Ståhl & van Prooijen, 2018; Stanovich et al., 2016). We therefore wanted to control for them to see whether scientific reasoning contributes to susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases over and above them.

Method

Participants

Our sample consisted of 317 participants (59% women) aged 18–30 years ($M = 23.32$, $SD = 3.557$). Part of the sample ($n = 117$) were university students who were awarded course credits for their participation. The remainder of the sample ($n = 200$) was recruited through a Slovak participant recruitment agency. The participants were selected to represent the young general population comparable to the rest of the previously collected sample, but more balanced in terms of gender and education and were given gift vouchers for taking part in the study. For this paper, the two subsamples were combined for analytical purposes². No data were analysed before the data

² Our initial aim was to collect data from the university student sample. However, in the time allocated for the data collection, a relatively low number of students agreed to participate. As we aimed for a larger sample (taking into account the sample size requirements for regression analyses with multiple predictors), and as the university student subsample proved very gender imbalanced (77% of the subsample were female), we decided to collect an

collection had been completed. A sensitivity power analysis indicated that a sample of this size should provide at least 80% power to detect any correlations of $r > .16$ with 5% error probability.

Materials

Scientific reasoning. Scientific-reasoning skills were measured using the Scientific-Reasoning Scale (SRS) developed by Drummond and Fischhoff (2017). The SRS consists of 11 short scenarios which test participants' knowledge of basic scientific concepts, such as confounding variables, control group, or random assignment to conditions. Example of scenario focused on random assignment to conditions is: "Researchers want to see whether a health intervention helps school children to lose weight. School children are sorted into either an intervention or control group." Each scenario is then followed by a statement, and participants are asked to indicate whether it is true or false: "The researchers should assign the overweight children to the intervention group." In this study, we included a third option 'I don't know' to reduce the probability of participants randomly guessing at the correct answer. The SRS score was computed by summing the correct answers to 11 items.

additional subsample of young adults under 30 years of age with the use of a participant recruitment agency. The results for this study were not analysed before the data collection from both subsamples was completed. For the purpose of all present analyses, the data from both subsamples were combined. However, for an interested reader, in the supplementary material we present comparisons of the two subsamples in all of the variables under study, as well as the key regression analyses (see below) repeated while controlling for the study subsample. Although the two subsamples did differ somewhat in their scores on some of the measures, the results of the regression analyses after controlling for study subsample were completely consistent with the conclusions presented in the main manuscript.

Cognitive ability. The Vienna Matrix Test (VMT; Klose, Černochová, & Král, 2002) was used as the standardised test of participants' cognitive abilities. The test is similar to Raven's Progressive Matrices and the authors of the Czech adaptation reported a strong correlation ($r = .92$) between the two measures. The VMT consists of 24 items of increasing difficulty in which participants have to identify the pattern in a complex 3 x 3 picture matrix and choose one of eight options to complete the figure.

Thinking dispositions. Two measures were used to tap into participants' thinking dispositions. To measure analytic thinking disposition, we used the *20-item rational subscale of the Rational-Experiential Inventory* (REI-R; Pacini & Epstein, 1999). The REI-R is based on the Need for Cognition scale (Epstein, Pacini, Denes-Raj, & Heier, 1996) and measures appraisal of intellectual challenges, complex thinking, and logical deliberation. An example item on the REI-R is: 'I enjoy solving problems that require hard thinking.' Secondly, we used the *20-item Dogmatism Scale* (DOG, Altemeyer, 2002) to measure closed-mindedness and how much people cling to attitudes despite having counterfactual evidence (e.g., 'There are no discoveries or facts that could possibly make me change my mind about the things that matter most in life.'). Participants were asked to rate their agreement with items from both measures on a scale from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 6 (*strongly agree*).

Epistemically suspect beliefs. We used a 34-item self-report measure to study the degree to which participants held various epistemically suspect beliefs. This measure was composed of the 26-item Revised Paranormal Belief Scale (Tobacyk, 2004) and eight items were newly created or adapted from our previous work (Čavoјová & Ballová Mikušková, 2014); four of which were concerned with conspiracy beliefs about global warming, refugees, juvenile justice, and mobile technologies, and the other four pertaining to pseudoscientific beliefs related to the domain of health, which measured

the degree to which participants believe in the effectiveness of homeopathy, wearing crystals, and undergoing detox. The items were mixed up and participants were asked to express the degree to which they believe in each statement using a percentual scale (0–100%). Participants' average scores were then calculated based on all 34 items and were subsequently used as a composite index of participant susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs³.

Heuristics and biases tasks. Several problems from the heuristics and biases literature were used to study participants' general susceptibility to cognitive biases. These were four syllogistic-reasoning tasks, three ratio bias problems, seven items resembling the Cognitive Reflection Test, and four selection tasks. Short descriptions of each type of reasoning problem are given in the Supplementary Material. Responses to the 18 tasks were summed to form a single composite score for each participant and reversed so a higher value indicates a higher susceptibility to cognitive biases.

Procedure

The study was administered via an online survey and was completed during two online sessions in order to avoid participant fatigue. In the first session participants completed a questionnaire derived from epistemically suspect beliefs, heuristics, and biases problems, the Scientific-Reasoning Scale, thinking-disposition measures, and several

³ For completeness, in the supplementary materials we also present descriptive statistics and correlations pertaining to each of the three types of epistemically suspect beliefs, i.e. paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs, separately. As in previous research (e.g. Lobato et al., 2014), the three types of epistemically suspect beliefs were shown to be substantially mutually intercorrelated and exhibited largely consistent patterns of correlations with individual difference measures in the present study, albeit with slight dissimilarities (see Table S3 in the supplementary material).

other short measures not reported here. In the second session, the participants were given the Vienna Matrix Test only.

Results⁴

Descriptive statistics for all the measures used in the study and their mutual correlations are presented in Table 1. On average, our participants were relatively sceptical towards the various claims in the epistemically suspect beliefs questionnaire, with only approximately 20% of the sample being more inclined to believe in them (i.e., had an average score of more than 50). On the other hand, as can be seen from the average bias susceptibility score, participants exhibited biased reasoning on 65% of the heuristics and biases problems (a higher bias susceptibility score indicates more biased reasoning).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics and correlations between all measures used in the study

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	α	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.
1. Scientific reasoning	4.91	2.41	.60	1				
2. Cognitive ability	14.66	5.98	.90	.366	1			
3. Analytic-thinking disp.	3.82	0.69	.87	.203	.225	1		
4. Dogmatism	2.94	0.62	.82	-.261	-.258	-.087	1	
5. Epistemically suspect beliefs	33.82	16.89	.92	-.209	-.211	-.078	.134	1
6. Bias susceptibility	11.58	2.94	.66	-.379	-.440	-.182	.204	.149

Note. $N = 317$. The table shows the mean score, standard deviations, and internal consistency of the measures reported in the study. Correlations that appear in bold are significant. Correlations of $r > .111$ are significant at $p = .05$, correlations of $r > .145$ are significant at $p = .01$, and correlations of $r > .184$ are significant at $p = .001$.

⁴ The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at osf.io/gpfmh.

As the first step in our analysis, we explored the correlations between susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases, and their presumed cognitive predictors. As can be seen from the Table 1, scientific reasoning, cognitive ability, and thinking dispositions all correlated with both susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs and susceptibility to various reasoning biases. The only exception was the non-significant relationship between analytic-thinking disposition and susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs. As expected, better scientific reasoning, higher cognitive ability, and analytic-thinking disposition were related to weaker susceptibility to biases in reasoning and acceptance of unsubstantiated beliefs. Dogmatism, on the other hand, was positively related both to epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases. A visual inspection of the correlations also indicated that the individual-difference factors were more strongly related to susceptibility to cognitive biases than to acceptance of various epistemically suspect beliefs. Consistent with some previous research (Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015; Stanovich et al., 2016), susceptibility to cognitive biases was related to the acceptance of epistemically suspect beliefs, although in our study the relationship was quite weak.

While the correlational analysis pointed to cognitive ability, thinking dispositions, and scientific reasoning all playing a role in susceptibility to cognitive biases and to epistemically suspect beliefs, the three individual difference variables were themselves mutually correlated. Therefore, we conducted two regression analyses in order to ascertain (1) whether both cognitive ability and thinking dispositions independently predict susceptibility to cognitive biases and epistemically suspect beliefs, and (2) whether scientific reasoning skills will emerge as a significant predictor over and above cognitive ability and/or thinking dispositions. In both regressions, the variables were entered in three steps. Cognitive ability was entered first as it generally showed the

strongest relationship with the outcome variables in the correlation analysis. Then, both thinking disposition variables were added in the second step to ascertain whether they predicted variance in the outcome measures over and above general cognitive ability. Finally, scientific reasoning was entered in the final step to examine whether it explained any additional variance not accounted for by the other individual-difference variables in the analysis⁵.

In the first regression (Table 2), cognitive ability explained approximately 4% of variance in susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs. However, in the second step of the regression, neither of the thinking disposition variables predicted epistemically suspect beliefs. Crucially, scientific reasoning emerged as a significant predictor in the last step of the regression ($b = .140$), explaining around 2% of the variance in epistemically suspect beliefs over and above cognitive ability and thinking dispositions. In the final model, both cognitive ability and scientific reasoning independently predicted acceptance of various epistemically suspect beliefs and to a very similar extent, but neither analytic-thinking disposition, nor dogmatism emerged as significant predictors when cognitive ability and scientific reasoning were taken into account. However, as can be seen from the overall low regression coefficients, the overall

⁵ The individual difference measures used as predictors in both of our regressions were shown above to be substantially mutually intercorrelated which indicates a potential problem with multicollinearity for our regression analyses. To make sure that the estimates of regression coefficients presented in Tables 2 and 3 are not biased, we have calculated Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) as multicollinearity diagnostic measure for the predictors included in both of our regressions. However, all of the VIF values were low (largest VIF = 1.227) and far from the threshold of VIF > 10, which is usually considered problematic (e.g. Field, 2013).

regression model explained relatively little of the variance (6%) in susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs.

Table 2. Summary of the regression analysis predicting acceptance of epistemically suspect beliefs

	<i>b</i> (<i>SE</i>)	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Step 1				
Constant	42.54 (2.46)		17.28	<i>p</i> < .001
Cognitive ability	-0.60 (0.16)	-.211	-3.82	<i>p</i> < .001
$R^2 = .041, F(1,315) = 14.62, p < .001$				
Step 2				
Constant	37.32 (7.56)		4.94	<i>p</i> < .001
Cognitive ability	-0.52 (0.17)	-.182	-3.13	<i>p</i> = .002
Analytic-thinking disp.	-0.71 (1.38)	-.029	-0.52	<i>p</i> = .606
Dogmatism	2.30 (1.56)	.084	1.48	<i>p</i> = .141
$\Delta R^2 = .008, F(2,313) = 1.25, p = .289$				
Step 3				
Constant	40.80 (7.65)		5.33	<i>p</i> < .001
Cognitive ability	-0.40 (0.17)	-.141	-2.33	<i>p</i> = .020
Analytic-thinking disp.	-0.30 (1.38)	-.012	-0.22	<i>p</i> = .829
Dogmatism	1.63 (1.57)	.060	1.04	<i>p</i> = .301
Scientific reasoning	-0.98 (0.42)	-.140	-2.32	<i>p</i> = .021
$\Delta R^2 = .016, F(1,312) = 5.37, p = .021$				

Note. The table shows standardised (β) and unstandardised regression coefficients (*b*) with their respective *t*-values and significance. R^2 and ΔR^2 denote the adjusted r-square for the initial model and changes in r-square at the 2nd and 3rd steps of the regression with the appropriate statistical change. Significant predictors are presented in bold.

In the second regression (Table 3), cognitive ability emerged as a substantial predictor in the first step of the analysis. The two thinking-disposition variables entered in the second step led to around a 2% increase in explained variance of the model; however,

when cognitive ability had been taken into account, neither analytic-thinking disposition nor dogmatism significantly predicted susceptibility to cognitive biases.. Still, as could be expected, the REI-R was negatively related to bias susceptibility, indicating that participants with a higher analytic-thinking disposition showed fewer cognitive biases, while the opposite was true for dogmatism. Crucially, entering scientific reasoning into the model as well explained an additional 4.5% of explained variance in susceptibility to cognitive biases. While both cognitive ability and scientific reasoning independently predicted bias susceptibility, cognitive ability played a slightly more important role in this last model than did scientific reasoning. Neither of the two thinking-disposition measures predicted susceptibility to cognitive biases after accounting for differences in cognitive ability and scientific reasoning. Together, the variables explained more than 24% of the variance in the performance on reasoning problems.

Table 3. Summary of the regression analysis predicting bias susceptibility

	<i>b</i> (<i>SE</i>)	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Step 1				
Constant	14.75 (0.39)		37.44	<i>p</i> < .001
Cognitive ability	-0.22 (0.03)	-.440	-8.69	<i>p</i> < .001
$R^2 = .191, F(1,315) = 75.57, p < .001$				
Step 2				
Constant	14.50 (1.20)		12.06	<i>p</i> < .001
Cognitive ability	-0.20 (0.03)	-.396	-7.45	<i>p</i> < .001
Analytic-thinking disp.	-0.36 (0.22)	-.085	-1.64	<i>p</i> = .102
Dogmatism	0.45 (0.25)	.094	1.81	<i>p</i> = .072
$\Delta R^2 = .016, F(2,313) = 3.07, p = .048$				
Step 3				
Constant	15.52 (1.19)		13.01	<i>p</i> < .001
Cognitive ability	-0.16 (0.03)	-.328	-6.05	<i>p</i> < .001
Analytic-thinking disp.	-0.24 (0.22)	-.056	-1.11	<i>p</i> = .267
Dogmatism	0.25 (0.25)	.053	1.03	<i>p</i> = .304
Scientific reasoning	-0.29 (0.07)	-.234	-4.34	<i>p</i> < .001
$\Delta R^2 = .045, F(1,312) = 18.84, p < .001$				

Note. The table contains standardised (β) and unstandardised regression coefficients (*b*) with their respective *t*-values and significance. R^2 and ΔR^2 denote the adjusted r-square for the initial model and change in r-square at the 2nd and 3rd steps of the regression with appropriate change statistics. Significant predictors are presented in bold.

Discussion

In this study we examined whether scientific-reasoning skills can predict people's susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive biases over and above thinking dispositions and cognitive ability, two of the most studied cognitive predictors. As expected, scientific reasoning correlated positively with dispositions towards analytic thinking and cognitive ability and negatively with dogmatism, epistemically

suspect beliefs, and susceptibility to cognitive biases. Most importantly, it emerged as a significant predictor, contributing to both susceptibility to cognitive biases and to epistemically suspect beliefs over and above the other cognitive predictors. These results provide, as far as we are aware, the first empirical evidence that scientific-reasoning ability is a significant factor in protecting against epistemically suspect beliefs, and in aiding better decision-making among the non-scientific population.

In the heuristics and biases research field, Stanovich (2018) has argued that researchers need to start focusing more on the mindware component of sound reasoning. Without properly instantiated mindware, no amount of other processing requirements, such as cognitive ability and thinking dispositions, can aid reasoning as people cannot make appropriate use of their capabilities if they are unable to identify the logical principles required to solve the problem. In line with this view, we found that scientific reasoning not only correlated moderately with participants' composite bias-susceptibility scores, but substantially contributed to bias susceptibility over and above thinking dispositions and cognitive ability. Similar results were recently reported by Šrol and De Neys (n.d.), who also found a mindware instantiation index, although of a different kind, to be an important predictor of performance on heuristics and biases problems. Interestingly, neither of the two thinking-disposition indicators in our study predicted bias susceptibility over cognitive ability, in contrast to past research findings (Klaczynski, 2014; Šrol & Neys, n.d.; Toplak et al., 2011). However, this might be partly due to the nature of our heuristics and biases battery which consisted of problems requiring some kind of probabilistic-, logic-, or scientific-reasoning mindware. Thus, finding the correct answer may depend more on these knowledge requirements than on thinking dispositions and other processing requirements.

In comparison with bias susceptibility, cognitive predictors played a subtler role in the acceptance of epistemically suspect beliefs. This was already visible in the correlation analysis where epistemically suspect beliefs tended to correlate weakly with other individual-difference measures, and non-significantly in the case of analytic-thinking disposition. This latter finding probably reflects the previously documented finding that various epistemically suspect beliefs tend to be more strongly related to intuitive-thinking disposition than to analytic-thinking disposition (Genovese, 2005; Lobato & Zimmerman, 2018; Wolfradt et al., 1999). On the other hand, in our study, the size of the correlation between epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive ability is relatively consistent with previous research, which has tended to show relatively weak relationships between various intelligence measures and some epistemically suspect beliefs (Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015; Ståhl & van Prooijen, 2018), and no relationship at all where some beliefs are concerned (e.g., Ballová Mikušková, 2018; Čavojová & Jurkovič, 2017).

And yet, both intelligence and scientific-reasoning ability emerged as significant independent predictors of susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs in the regression model. While there is already some research on the role of scientific literacy in protecting against epistemically suspect beliefs (Fasce & Picó, 2019), we believe our findings to be the first empirical evidence of the role scientific-reasoning ability may play in this regard. There are several ways in which more pronounced scientific-reasoning abilities may lead to weaker susceptibility to epistemically suspect beliefs. First, the ability to objectively evaluate evidence may substantially help a person see that the various ‘alternative explanations’ upon which conspiracy theories, pseudoscientific beliefs and the like are based upon depend on unsubstantiated claims. Also, people with a higher level of scientific reasoning have been shown to hold beliefs

more consistent with the scientific consensus (Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017), therefore, they should be less likely to adopt beliefs based on claims that have been directly disproven by science, such as those associated with many paranormal phenomena (Hines, 2002).

However, it should be noted that more pronounced scientific reasoning skills are unlikely to constitute a panacea for protecting against unfounded beliefs. For example, Kahan (2013) showed that better scientific literacy does not reduce climate-change rejection, but in contrast, leads to greater polarisation among people subscribing to conservative ideology. Thus, some beliefs (that can be considered unfounded in scientific evidence, such as those included in our measures) may reflect the group or cultural identity of individuals who use their cognitive abilities and scientific understanding to defend their beliefs rather than examine them critically. The effect of prior beliefs on reasoning is well documented in the literature on motivated reasoning and my-side bias (Baron, 1995; Čavojová, Šrol, & Adamus, 2018; Klaczynski & Gordon, 1996; Stanovich & West, 2008a). Therefore, it may be that people with more pronounced scientific reasoning and general cognitive abilities are more sceptical of epistemically suspect beliefs that go against their prior attitudes, but that this does not apply to unfounded beliefs that are better aligned with their political or religious affiliation. This might be the reason why, in our study, cognitive ability and scientific reasoning predicted relatively little variance in epistemically suspect beliefs. While this is just conjecture, we hope future research will investigate how scientific reasoning interacts with religious and political affiliation in relation to the adoption and acceptance of epistemically suspect beliefs.

Also, in our sample the average performance on the Scientific-Reasoning Scale (45%) was somewhat lower than the success rates on the final 11-item measure originally

reported by Drummond and Fischhoff (2017), which ranged between 61% and 63%. This may suggest that the scale is slightly more difficult for the general public, which in turn may result in lower variability and floor effects, and could be why we observed relatively low reliability for the SRS. But the difference in accuracy between our sample and the original findings might also partly reflect the school system in Slovakia, as there is arguably less emphasis on critical and scientific thinking in the Slovak secondary school curriculum than in some other western education systems⁶. In examining any differences between our results and results of the original study we have to take into account that we introduced a third option (I don't know) to true/false responses. The rationale behind this decision was to decrease the guessing and thus increase the validity of responses. In average about 15 % of participants responded with "I don't know" to each item. Perhaps some of the observed decrease in performance compared to results reported by Drummond and Fischhoff (2017) can be attributed to decrease in correct, but random answers, in absence of 'I don't know' option. We can speculate that when participants face only two choices (true/false) some of those who have no clue about the right answer would guess correctly by chance alone, and thus possibly inflating the score of correct answers.

⁶ For example, Kosturková (2013) examined the critical thinking skills of Slovak teachers using the Watson–Glaser test of critical thinking. The teachers' scores were surprisingly low; when compared with the results of British applicants to the teaching profession, the results of the Slovak secondary school teachers were on average 23.10 points lower. Moreover, the best participant in Kosturková's study corresponded to the 20th percentile in the British referential data. This result was attributed to the focus in the Slovak school system on rote learning instead of critical thinking.

An alternative explanation as to why the individual-difference measures were less good at predicting epistemically suspect beliefs in our study could be that while susceptibility to heuristics and biases is known to be primarily dependent on cognitive factors such as the ones employed in this study, the research on epistemically suspect beliefs has also uncovered a broader spectrum of various other cognitive, social, and personality predictors. These include paranoid ideation, authoritarian personality (Čavoјová & Jurkovič, 2017), the need for closure (Leman & Cinnirella, 2013; Marchlewska, Cichocka, & Kossowska, 2017), political ideology (Lobato & Zimmerman, 2018), religious affiliation and religious fundamentalism, neuroticism, and extraversion (Lobato et al., 2014). Therefore, the low level of explained variance in the acceptance of epistemically suspect beliefs may also be because we focused on the cognitive predictors of these beliefs and failed to take into account some other individual-difference variables.

Also, notably, neither of the thinking-disposition indicators emerged as significant in predicting epistemically suspect beliefs. This was surprising as previous research had shown moderate relationships between various epistemically suspect beliefs and indicators of intuitive- and analytic-thinking dispositions (Aarnio & Lindeman, 2005; Lindeman & Aarnio, 2006a; Lobato et al., 2014; Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015; Stanovich et al., 2016), although the latter are usually thought to have a less pronounced role in the acceptance of epistemically suspect beliefs than the former. Maybe some other measure, such as actively open thinking, might show stronger relationships than our thinking dispositions indicators, but we suspect that it would still be relatively weak, as actively open minded thinking measure comprises of the items from Dogmatism subscale as well (Stanovich & West, 1997).

Overall, the weak role of our thinking-disposition predictors might be because, as Ståhl and van Prooijen (2018) have shown, the ability to reason analytically is not sufficient for unfounded beliefs to be rejected; people have to strongly value epistemic rationality before they can become sufficiently motivated to use their analytic skills to scrutinise suspicious claims. Therefore, it is possible that in the absence of such motivation their thinking dispositions will only be weakly predictive of the acceptance of various epistemically suspect claims. However, as we did not employ a measure of how much our participants valued epistemic rationality, we cannot establish whether this was the case in our study.

In modern society, scientific-reasoning skills are becoming increasingly important in navigating many aspects of everyday life, from being alert to unsubstantiated claims and fake reports in newspapers and social media, to being able to process the complex information around us and make rational decisions regarding health, finances, and other important issues. In our study, we have shown that scientific reasoning did indeed help protect people against paranormal, pseudoscientific, and conspiracy beliefs, and also contributed to sound reasoning on a host of heuristic and biases tasks. Although the role of scientific reasoning may not have been particularly strong, in both cases it emerged as a predictor over other cognitive predictors in the analysis. Nonetheless, subsequent research is needed to examine whether scientific reasoning helps to universally protect against epistemically suspect beliefs, or whether it only helps people with motivated reasoning adopt beliefs which are consistent with their established positions, such as political and religious affiliation (Kahan, 2013). Nevertheless, we believe our conclusions provide further evidence for the ever increasing need to improve civic scientific literacy (e.g., Lobato & Zimmerman, 2018).

References

- Aarnio, K., & Lindeman, M. (2005). Paranormal beliefs, education, and thinking styles. *Personality and Individual Differences, 39*(7), 1227–1236.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2005.04.009>
- Altemeyer, B. (2002). Dogmatic behavior among students: testing a new measure of dogmatism. *The Journal of Social Psychology, 142*(6), 713–721.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00224540209603931>
- Ballová Mikušková, E. (2018). Conspiracy beliefs of future teachers. *Current Psychology, 37*(3), 692–701. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-017-9561-4>
- Baron, J. (1995). Myside bias in thinking about abortion. *Thinking & Reasoning, 1*(3), 221–235. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13546789508256909>
- Bensley, D. A., Lilienfeld, S. O., & Powell, L. A. (2014). A new measure of psychological misconceptions: Relations with academic background, critical thinking, and acceptance of paranormal and pseudoscientific claims. *Learning and Individual Differences, 36*, 9–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2014.07.009>
- Brotherton, R., & French, C. C. (2014). Belief in conspiracy theories and susceptibility to the conjunction fallacy. *Applied Cognitive Psychology, 28*(2), 238–248.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.2995>
- Brugger, P., & Graves, R. E. (1997). Testing vs. believing hypotheses: Magical ideation in the judgment of contingencies. *Cognitive Neuropsychiatry, 2*(4), 251–272.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/135468097396270>
- Čavojová, V., & Ballová Mikušková, E. (2014). Developing Contaminated Mindware Measure. In *Proceedings of INTED2014 Conference 10th-12th March 2014, Valencia, Spain* (pp. 2530–2537). Valencia.
- Čavojová, V., & Jurkovič, M. (2017). Intuition and irrationality. In L. Pitel (Ed.), *Sociálne procesy a osobnosť 2016* (pp. 77–83). Bratislava: Ústav experimentálnej psychológie, CSPV SAV. Retrieved from <http://www.spao.eu/pastevents.php>
- Čavojová, V., Secară, E. C., Jurkovič, M., & Šrol, J. (2018). Reception and willingness to share pseudo-profound bullshit and their relation to other epistemically suspect beliefs and cognitive ability in Slovakia and Romania. *Applied Cognitive Psychology, 1*–13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.3486>
- Čavojová, V., Šrol, J., & Adamus, M. (2018). My point is valid, yours is not: myside bias in reasoning about abortion. *Journal of Cognitive Psychology, 30*(7), 656–669.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/20445911.2018.1518961>

- De Neys, W., & Bonnefon, J. F. (2013). The “whys” and “whens” of individual differences in thinking biases. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *17*(4), 172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2013.02.001>
- Díaz-Vilela, L., & Alvarez, C. J. (2004). Differences in paranormal beliefs across fields of study from a Spanish adaptation of Tobacyk’s RPBS. *The Journal of Parapsychology*, *68*(2), 405–421.
- Drummond, C., & Fischhoff, B. (2017). Development and validation of the Scientific Reasoning Scale. *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making*, *30*(1), 26–38. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bdm.1906>
- Dunbar, K. N., & Fugelsang, J. A. (2005). Scientific thinking and reasoning. In K. J. Holyoak & R. G. Morrison (Eds.), *Cambridge handbook of thinking and reasoning* (pp. 705–725). New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Dunbar, K. N., & Klahr, D. (2012). Scientific thinking and reasoning. In K. J. Holyoak & R. G. Morrison (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Thinking and Reasoning* (pp. 701–718). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199734689.013.0035>
- Epstein, S., Pacini, R., Denes-Raj, V., & Heier, H. (1996). Individual differences in intuitive-experiential and analytical-rational thinking styles. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *71*(2), 390–405. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.71.2.390>
- Fasce, A., & Picó, A. (2019). Science as a Vaccine. *Science & Education*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11191-018-00022-0>
- Genovese, J. E. C. (2005). Paranormal beliefs, schizotypy, and thinking styles among teachers and future teachers. *Personality and Individual Differences*, *39*(1), 93–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2004.12.008>
- Goode, E. (2002). Education, scientific knowledge, and belief in paranormal. *The Skeptical Inquirer*, *26*(1), 24–27. Retrieved from [http://www.siths.org/ourpages/auto/2010/10/3/54135565/4 education science and paranormal.pdf](http://www.siths.org/ourpages/auto/2010/10/3/54135565/4%20education%20science%20and%20paranormal.pdf)
- Grimmer, M. R., & White, K. D. (1992). Nonconventional beliefs among australian science and nonscience students. *Journal of Psychology: Interdisciplinary and Applied*, *126*(5), 521–528. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.1992.10543385>
- Harambam, J., & Aupers, S. (2015). Contesting epistemic authority: Conspiracy theories on the boundaries of science. *Public Understanding of Science*, *24*(4),

- 466–480. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662514559891>
- Hergovich, A., & Arendasy, M. (2005). Critical thinking ability and belief in the paranormal. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 38(8), 1805–1812.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2004.11.008>
- Hines, T. (2002). *Pseudoscience and the paranormal*. New York: Prometheus Books.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ejoc.201200111>
- Johnson, M., & Pigliucci, M. (2004). Is knowledge of science associated with higher skepticism of pseudoscientific claims? *The American Biology Teacher*, 66(8), 536–548. <https://doi.org/10.2307/4451737>
- Kahan, D. M. (2013). Ideology, motivated reasoning, and cognitive reflection. *Judgement and Decision Making*, 8(4), 407–424. <https://doi.org/2013-28010-002>
- Kahan, D. M. (2017). “Ordinary Science Intelligence”: A Science comprehension measure for use in the study of risk perception and science communication. *Journal of Risk Research*, 20(8), 995–1016.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2016.1148067>
- Kahan, D. M., Peters, E., Wittlin, M., Slovic, P., Ouellette, L. L., Braman, D., & Mandel, G. (2012). The polarizing impact of science literacy and numeracy on perceived climate change risks. *Nature Climate Change*, 2(10), 732–735.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1547>
- Kahneman, D., & Frederick, S. (2002). Representativeness revisited: Attribute substitution in intuitive judgment. In T. Gilovich, D. Griffin, & D. Kahneman (Eds.), *Heuristics of Intuitive Judgment: Extensions and Applications* (pp. 1–30). New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Klaczynski, P. A. (2014). Heuristics and biases: Interactions among numeracy, ability, and reflectiveness predict normative responding. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 5, 1–13.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.00665>
- Klaczynski, P. A., & Gordon, D. H. (1996). Self-serving influences on adolescents’ evaluations of belief-relevant evidence. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 62(3), 317–339. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jecp.1996.0033>
- Klose, J., Černochová, D., & Král, P. (2002). *Vídeňský maticový test*. Praha: Testcentrum.
- Kosturková, M. (2013). Kritické myslenie pedagógov stredných škôl. *Pedagogika.Sk*, 4(4), 283–298.
- Leman, P. J., & Cinnirella, M. (2013). Beliefs in conspiracy theories and the need for

- cognitive closure. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4, 378.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00378>
- Lewandowsky, S., Gignac, G. E., & Oberauer, K. (2013). The role of conspiracist ideation and worldviews in predicting rejection of science. *PLoS ONE*, 8(10), e75637. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0075637>
- Lindeman, M., & Aarnio, K. (2006). Paranormal beliefs: Their dimensionality and correlates. *European Journal of Personality*, 20(7), 585–602.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/per.608>
- Lobato, E. J. C., & Zimmerman, C. (2018). Examining how people reason about controversial scientific topics. *Thinking and Reasoning*, 1–25.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00376456>
- Lobato, E., Mendoza, J., Sims, V., & Chin, M. (2014). Examining the relationship between conspiracy theories, paranormal beliefs, and pseudoscience acceptance among a university population. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 28(5), 617–625.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.3042>
- Lundström, M., & Jakobsson, A. (2009). Students' ideas regarding science and pseudoscience in relation to the human body and health. *Nord Dina*, 5(1), 3–17.
<https://doi.org/10.5617/nordina.279>
- Majima, Y. (2015). Belief in pseudoscience, cognitive style and science literacy. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 29(4), 552–559. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.3136>
- Marchlewska, M., Cichocka, A., & Kossowska, M. (2017). Addicted to answers: Need for cognitive closure and the endorsement of conspiracy beliefs. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 48, 109–117. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.2308>
- McCloskey, M. (1983). Intuitive physics. *Scientific American*, 248(4), 122–130.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/scientificamerican0483-122>
- Miller, J. D. (1983). Scientific Literacy: A Conceptual and Empirical Review. *Daedalus*, 112(2), 29–48. <https://doi.org/10.2307/20024852>
- Miller, J. D. (1998). The measurement of civic scientific literacy. *Public Understanding of Science*, 7(3), 203–223. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0963-6625/7/3/001>
- Miller, J. D. (2004). Public understanding of, and attitudes toward, scientific research: What we know and what we need to know. *Public Understanding of Science*, 13(3), 273–294. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662504044908>
- Pacini, R., & Epstein, S. (1999). The relation of rational and experiential information processing styles to personality, basic beliefs, and the ratio-bias phenomenon.

- Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 76(6), 972–987.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.76.6.972>
- Pennycook, G., Cheyne, J. A. A., Barr, N., Koehler, D. J., & Fugelsang, J. A. (2015). On the reception and detection of pseudo-profound bullshit. *Judgment and Decision Making*, 10(6), 549–563. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00279>
- Pennycook, G., Fugelsang, J. a., & Koehler, D. J. (2015). Everyday consequences of analytic thinking. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 24(6), 425–432. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721415604610>
- Rogers, P., Davis, T., & Fisk, J. (2009). Paranormal belief and susceptibility to the conjunction fallacy. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 23(4), 524–542. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp>
- Shtulman, A., & Valcarcel, J. (2012). Scientific knowledge suppresses but does not supplant earlier intuitions. *Cognition*, 124(2), 209–215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2012.04.005>
- Šrol, J., & Neys, W. De. (n.d.). Predicting individual differences in conflict detection and bias susceptibility during reasoning.
- Ståhl, T., & van Prooijen, J.-W. (2018). Epistemic rationality: Skepticism toward unfounded beliefs requires sufficient cognitive ability and motivation to be rational. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 122, 155–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2017.10.026>
- Stanovich, K. E. (2018). Miserliness in human cognition: The interaction of detection, override and mindware. *Thinking and Reasoning*, 24(4), 423–444. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13546783.2018.1459314>
- Stanovich, K. E., & West, R. F. (1997). Reasoning independently of prior belief and individual differences in actively open-minded thinking. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 89(2), 342–357.
- Stanovich, K. E., & West, R. F. (2008a). On the failure of cognitive ability to predict myside and one-sided thinking biases. *Thinking & Reasoning*, 14(2), 129–167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13546780701679764>
- Stanovich, K. E., & West, R. F. (2008b). On the relative independence of thinking biases and cognitive ability. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 94(4), 672–695. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.94.4.672>
- Stanovich, K. E., West, R. F., & Toplak, M. E. (2016). *The Rationality Quotient. Toward a Test of Rational Thinking*. MIT Press.

- Swami, V., Voracek, M., Stieger, S., Tran, U. S., & Furnham, A. (2014). Analytic thinking reduces belief in conspiracy theories. *Cognition*, *133*(3), 572–585. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2014.08.006>
- Tobacyk, J. J. (2004). A Revised Paranormal Belief Scale. *International Journal of Transpersonal Studies*, *23*(1), 94–98. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t14015-000>
- Toplak, M. E., West, R. F., & Stanovich, K. E. (2011). The Cognitive Reflection Test as a predictor of performance on heuristics-and-biases tasks. *Memory & Cognition*, *39*(7), 1275–1289. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13421-011-0104-1>
- Tsai, C. Y., Shein, P. P., Jack, B. M., Wu, K. C., Chou, C. Y., Wu, Y. Y., ... Huang, T. C. (2012). Effects of exposure to pseudoscientific television programs upon Taiwanese citizens' pseudoscientific beliefs. *International Journal of Science Education*, *2*(2), 175–194. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21548455.2011.610132>
- Tversky, A., & Kahneman, D. (1974). Judgment under uncertainty: Heuristics and biases. *Science*, *185*(4157), 1124–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.185.4157.1124>
- Walker, W. R., Hoekstra, S. J., & Vogl, R. J. (2002). Science education is no guarantee of skepticism. *Skeptic (Altadena, CA)*, *9*(3), 24–29. Retrieved from <http://go.galegroup.com/ps/anonymou?id=GALE%7CA91803905&sid=googleScholar&v=2.1&it=r&linkaccess=abs&issn=10639330&p=AONE&sw=w>
- Wolfradt, U., Oubaid, V., Straube, E. R., Bischoff, N., & Mischo, J. (1999). Thinking styles, schizotypal traits and anomalous experiences. *Personality and Individual Differences*, *27*(5), 821–830. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869\(99\)00031-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(99)00031-8)